

Yeast DNA Residue Assay Kits (qPCR) for Biological Research

Creative Diagnostics, a reagent supplier and developer focused on biologics quality control, is pleased to announce the launch of its new [Yeast DNA Residue Assay Kits](#) (qPCR) for detecting and quantifying yeast DNA residues in various samples. These innovative assay kits offer researchers a highly sensitive and accurate method to ensure product integrity and comply with industry standards.

As an expert in bioprocess impurity analysis, Creative Diagnostics offers Host Cell DNA Assay Kits to identify residual host cell DNA within various recombinant expression systems. These kits are applicable to a wide range of biological products, including those derived from mammalian, yeast, bacterial, viral, and insect cells. By utilizing these assays, researchers can obtain valuable information about host cell DNA contamination, enabling them to optimize bioprocesses and minimize the presence of such impurities.

Designed to meet the growing demand for accurate and efficient yeast DNA residue detection, Creative Diagnostics has introduced a new line of Yeast DNA Residue Assay Kits (qPCR) to help researchers address yeast contamination issues, including *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* DNA Residue Assay Kit, *Pichia pastoris* DNA Residue Assay Kit, *Hansenula polymorpha* DNA Residue Assay Kit, and Fungus DNA Residue Assay Kit, ideal for both research and routine testing applications.

For example, the Fungus DNA Residue Kit (Cat. No. DDNA-013) is designed for the qualitative detection of fungal contamination in cells, cell products, vaccines and other products. This kit employs PCR fluorescence probe technology to qualitatively detect the presence of fungal DNA in samples, covering approximately 92% of known fungal species and matching the DNA sequences of nearly 5,000 fungal species (or subspecies).

In addition, it has been tested for DNA from a wide range of fungal, non-fungal and common engineered cell species and has demonstrated good broad-spectrum and high specificity. The detection limit of the kit does not exceed 5 CFU/reaction. This kit is used in conjunction with the Creative Diagnostics Fungal DNA Extraction Kit (Magnetic Beads) to detect the presence of fungal contamination in biological samples.

The *Hansenula polymorpha* DNA Residue Assay Kit (Cat. No. DDNA-014) is a quantitative tool designed to measure the presence of residual *Hansenula polymorpha* DNA in a wide range of biological products, such as intermediates, semi-finished products, and finished goods. Utilizing the Taqman probe method, this kit offers rapid, highly specific, and reliable detection of *Hansenula polymorpha* DNA at femtogram levels. To ensure accurate results, the kit includes a *Hansenula polymorpha* DNA quantitative reference standard and is intended for use in

conjunction with Creative Diagnostics Host Cell DNA Prep Kit.

For more information on custom Yeast DNA Residue Assay Kits (qPCR) or project-specific Host Cell DNA Assay Kit development services, please visit <https://qbd.creative-diagnostics.com/products/yeast-dna-residue-assay-kits-qpcr-2778.html>.

About Creative Diagnostics

Creative Diagnostics is a global leader in the development and manufacturing of innovative tools and reagents for bioprocess impurity analysis. The company offers a comprehensive portfolio of solutions to support researchers in the quality control of biologics and provides biopharmaceutical quality, purity and safety assays, analytical methods and applications for the biotechnology and biopharmaceutical industries.